

Supporting Information

Promoting effect of interfacial hole accumulation on photoelectrochemical water oxidation in BiVO₄ and Mo doped BiVO₄

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Figure S1 XRD patterns (a) of as-synthesized BVO and Mo-BVO samples and corresponding zoomed region (b) of (121) crystal facet in BVO and Mo-BVO samples.

Figure S2 SEM images of BVO (a), Mo-BVO (c), and cross-section views of BVO (b) and Mo-BVO (d) sample.

Figure S3 UV-Vis-NIR absorption spectra (a) and corresponding Tauc plots (b) of ITO substrates, BVO, and Mo-BVO samples, assuming direct optical absorption.

Figure S4 High resolution XPS spectra of BVO and Mo-BVO samples: Bi 4f (a), V 2p (b), O 1s (c), N 1s (d), Mo 3d (e), and C 1s (f) spectral regions.

Figure S5 Raman spectra (532 nm excitation wavelength) of BVO (pink) and Mo-BVO (light brown) films. The FTO substrates (black) were measured as reference.

Figure S6 Current-voltage curves of BVO (a) and Mo-BVO (b) films, measured at a sweep rate of 10 mV s^{-1} in the dark and under illumination. The light intensity varies from 10 to 200 mW cm^{-2} .

Table S1 Positions of flat band potentials (E_{fb}) and concentrations of charge carriers in the dark and under illumination, estimated from the Mott–Schottky plots of the as-prepared BVO and Mo-BVO samples

Sample	Illumination intensity (mW cm ⁻²)	E_{fb} (V vs. RHE)	Concentration of charge carriers (10 ¹⁹ cm ⁻³)
BVO	0 (dark)	0.36	7.38
	10	0.36	7.42
	20	0.36	7.51
	50	0.36	7.64
	100	0.36	7.80
	150	0.36	7.91
	200	0.36	8.03
Mo-BVO	0 (dark)	0.53	5.12
	10	0.53	5.20
	20	0.53	5.27
	50	0.53	5.66
	100	0.53	5.72
	150	0.53	5.87
	200	0.53	5.97

Figure S7 Crystal structure of monoclinic BiVO_4 . Bismuth atoms (blue), Oxygen atoms (light red) and Vanadium atoms (dark red) are indicated, respectively.

Figure S8 Linear sweep voltammetry curves of BVO and Mo-BVO films samples, measured at a sweep rate of 10 mV s⁻¹ in the dark. The applied potential varies from 0.2 V to 2.2 V vs. RHE.

Figure S9 Secondary electron cutoff energies and valence band maximum position determination of BVO and Mo-BVO samples, measured by UPS. For the secondary electron cutoff determination, a bias of -6 V was applied to the sample and the spectra were subsequently corrected.

Figure S10 Chopped photocurrent density curves of BVO and Mo-BVO samples, measured at 1.2 V vs. RHE in 0.1 M phosphate buffer solution (pH 6.8).

Figure S11 Chopped light voltammetry curves of BVO and Mo-BVO samples, measured in 0.1 M phosphate buffer solution. The scan rate and light intensity were set to 50 mV s⁻¹ and 100 mW cm⁻², respectively.

Figure S12 Incident Photon-Electron Conversion Efficiency (IPCE) of BVO and Mo-BVO samples, measured at 1.23 V vs. RHE in 0.1 M phosphate buffer solution.

Figure S13 Cyclic voltammograms of BVO and Mo-BVO samples were conducted in a non-Faradaic region in 0.1 M phosphate buffer solution (pH 6.8) at the scan rates of 10, 20, 30, 40 and 50 mV s^{-1} . (a and b) Electric double layer capacitances of BVO and Mo-BVO samples were measured for determining electrochemical active surface area (ECSA). (c and d)

Description of the surface hole model

The semiconductor-electrolyte interface is similar to a semiconductor metal junction as illustrated in **Figure S14**. Free electrons in the semiconductor will flow to the electrolyte after contacting due to the difference of their work function. Charge transfer reaches a balance until the Fermi energy of the semiconductor (E_f) equals to that of the solution (E_{sol}). Band bending and space charge region in the semiconductor are subsequently formed for compensating the loss of electrons during the process.

Figure S14 Illustration of an n-type semiconductor electrolyte interface before (a) and after contact (b). The shallow ionized donor species and free electrons are denoted as “+” and “-” markers, respectively. Φ_s and Φ_{sol} are the work function of the semiconductor and the redox electrolyte, W is the width of space charge region.

The total positive charge number N_{total} in the depletion region of a semiconductor can be expressed as follows:

$$N_{total} = (N_{D^+} + p) A_c W \text{ (eqn. S1)}$$

where N_{D^+} , p and A_c represent the ionized donor density, free hole density and actual contacted area with electrolyte, respectively.

Assuming donors are completely ionized,

$$N_{D^+} = N_D = n_b \text{ (eqn. S2)}$$

where N_D and n_b represent donor density and bulk electron density of semiconductor, respectively, which are far larger than hole density p in depletion layer of an n-type semiconductor ($N_{D^+} \gg p$). Therefore, equation S1 can be simplified to:

$$N_{total} = N_D A_c W \text{ (eqn. S3)}$$

N_D is donor density, which is commonly used in the Mott-Schottky equation:

$$\frac{1}{C^2} = \frac{2}{e N_D \epsilon_0 \epsilon_s A_c^2} \left(U - U_{fb} - \frac{kT}{e} \right) \text{ (eqn. S4)}$$

C is the space charge layer capacitance of the semiconductor, e is elementary charge 1.60×10^{-19} C, ϵ_0 is the dielectric constant in vacuum (8.85×10^{-14} F cm⁻¹), ϵ_r is relative dielectric constant of the semiconductor. A_c is the actual illuminated surface area, U_{fb} is the flat band potential, k Boltzmann constant, T temperature in Kelvin.

In the case of illumination, an equal number of holes and electrons are generated within the space charge region of the semiconductor. However, photogenerated electrons will flow into the bulk due to band bending and photogenerated holes accumulate in the space charge region. This leads to quasi-Fermi level splitting for holes (E_h) and electrons (E_e). The process is illustrated in **Figure S15**. Therefore, the total positive charge number will change to N'_{total} , which may be written as follows:

$$N'_{total} = (N_D + \Delta p) A_c W' = N'_D A_c W' \text{ (eqn. S5)}$$

Δp represents the photogenerated hole density (unit: cm⁻³), N'_D represents the donor density under illumination, which can be calculated from the slope of the Mott-Schottky plot under illumination. W' is the width of space charge region under illumination.

The total number of photogenerated holes (ΔN_{total}) can be written as,

$$\Delta N_{total} = N'_{total} - N_{total} = \Delta p A_c W = N'_D A_c W' - N_D A_c W \text{ (eqn. S6)}$$

Where, N'_D and W' can be represented as,

$$N'_D = \frac{2}{\text{slope}' e \epsilon_0 \epsilon_s A_c^2} \text{ and } N_D = \frac{2}{\text{slope} e \epsilon_0 \epsilon_s A_c^2} \text{ (eqn. S7)}$$

$$W' = \sqrt{\frac{2\epsilon_0 \epsilon_s (U - U'_{fb})}{e N'_D}} \text{ and } W = \sqrt{\frac{2\epsilon_0 \epsilon_s (U - U_{fb})}{e N_D}} \text{ (eqn. S8)}$$

Figure S15 Schematic illustration of the band diagram variation of a semiconductor in the dark (a) and under illumination (b). The band bending of the semiconductor depends on the applied potential and light illumination intensity. Besides, quasi-Fermi levels of electrons (E_e) and holes (E_h) in the semiconductor will emerge under illumination. “+” markers represent the shallow ionized donor species.

Distribution of photogenerated holes within space charge region

The photoexcited holes will transfer to and accumulate at the surface. This process is illustrated in **Figure S16**. The accumulated charge carriers in the space charge region follow the Fermi-Dirac distribution, which is given as follows:

$$f_h(E) = \frac{1}{e^{\frac{(\varepsilon_i - \mu)}{kT}} + 1} = \frac{1}{e^{\frac{E}{kT}} + 1} \quad (\text{eqn. S9})$$

where k is the Boltzmann constant, T is absolute temperature (K), μ is the total chemical potential of the photogenerated holes, herein, μ indicates the energy of valence band maximum (VBM) at the surface. ε_i is the energy state of a single hole. E is the energy difference between ε_i and μ .

Since the total probability of hole occupation (P_{total}) is 1, the integrated probability of finding a hole in the range from $-3 kT$ to 0 equals to 1.

$$P_{total} = N_c \int_{-3kT}^0 f_h(E) dE = 1 \quad (\text{eqn. S10})$$

where N_c is a normalization constant.

The surface hole density is p_s (unit: cm^{-2}). The hole density p_E at the energy state of E can be calculated by equation S7.

$$\frac{p_E}{p_s} = \frac{f_h(E)}{f_h(0)} = \frac{f_h(E)}{\frac{1}{e^0 + 1}} = 2f_h(E) \quad (\text{eqn. S11})$$

$$p_E = 2p_s f_h(E) \quad (\text{eqn. S12})$$

Therefore, the total number of photogenerated holes (ΔN_{total}) is integration of hole density over the energy from $-3 kT$ to 0.

$$\Delta N_{total} = A_i \int_{-3kT}^0 p_E N_c dE = 2p_s N_c A_c \int_{-3kT}^0 f_h(E) dE = 2p_s A_c P_{total} = 2p_s A_c \quad (\text{eqn. S13})$$

By combining eqn. S13 with eqn. S6, S7 and S8. we can finally derive the expression for the surface hole density p_s

$$p_s = 0.5 (N'_D W' - N_D W) = \frac{1}{e A_c} \left(\sqrt{\frac{U - U'_{fb}}{\text{slope}'}} - \sqrt{\frac{U - U_{fb}}{\text{slope}}} \right) \quad (\text{eqn. S14})$$

Slope' and slope is the slope of the Mott-Schottky plot under illumination and in the dark, respectively. U'_{fb} and U_{fb} is the flat band position under illumination and in the dark.

Figure S16 Proposed model for calculation of accumulated photogenerated hole concentration at the semiconductor electrolyte interface under illumination at a specific potential. p_s is the surface hole density and p_{3kT} is bulk hole density at the position where the energy of holes is 3 kT lower than that of p_s .

The band bending in the space charge region is commonly larger than 3 kT, even at open circuit potential (OCP). This means that almost all photogenerated holes accumulate within SCR and do not extend into the bulk. For example, the flat band positions of BVO and Mo-BVO are 0.36 and 0.53 V vs. RHE, respectively. (Table 1) The OCP values of BVO and Mo-BVO are around 0.65 V vs. RHE (not presented). In this work, the applied potential of 0.7 to 1.4 V vs. RHE are employed to investigate relationship between charge transfer rate and surface accumulated hole density.

Figure S17 SEM images of BVO and Mo-BVO samples before and after PEC measurements, BVO-fresh (a), Mo-BVO-fresh (b), BVO-spent (c), Mo-BVO-spent (d).

Figure S18 XRD patterns of BVO and Mo-BVO samples before and after PEC measurements, fresh BVO and Mo-BVO samples(a), spent BVO and Mo-BVO samples (b).

Figure S19 High resolution XPS spectra of Bi, V, O and Mo elements in BVO and Mo-BVO samples before and after PEC measurements, Bi 4f-fresh (a), Bi 4f-spent (b), V 2p-fresh (c), V 2p-spent (d), O 1s-fresh (e), O 1s-spent (f), Mo 3d-fresh (g) and Mo 3d-spent (h).

Except some changes in the O1s region energy range, the high-resolution Bi V and Mo XP spectra of BVO and Mo-BVO samples substantially remain after PEC measurements. The peaks of O 1s at 534.2 eV in both BVO and Mo-BVO samples remarkably increase, which can be interpreted to the increased oxygen-containing adsorbates on the BVO and Mo-BVO samples.